

Solar water disinfection in high-volume containers: Are naturally occurring substances attenuating factors of radiation?

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HIGHLIGHTS

- SODIS process in high-volume containers for water disinfection is feasible.
- Quantification of water composition in the distribution of radiation.
- Successful kinetic modelling for radiation attenuating substances in water.
- Solids and humic acids play a critical attenuating role in high-volume containers.
- Iron mainly attenuates radiation but also improves bacterial internal Photo-Fenton.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Access to safe drinking water is still a world challenge. The SODIS process is an easy and affordable household water treatment (HWT) for low income countries. The main limitations of its standard procedure are the low treated volume (2 L Polyethylene terephthalate [PET] bottles are commonly used) and the uncertainty in the required solar exposure time, which is strongly dependent on the water composition and irradiance. This work evaluates the use of high-volume (25 L) PET containers for the SODIS process, especially focusing on the effect of water composition on the efficacy of *E. coli* bacteria inactivation as a reference for faecal contamination. The optical properties (absorption and scattering) of the substances dissolved in the water were found to have a dramatic impact since the radiation distribution inside a high-volume container is not homogenous and strongly influences the disinfection rate. Simulation of the radiation distribution within the container allows modelling and predicting the required solar exposure time based on the average radiation intensity and its uniformity index as a function of the water composition. Bicarbonates, soluble carbohydrates, solids and humic acids greatly agreed with the model while iron was found to have a more complicated role since its main effect as attenuator of radiation is partially counteracted by the improvement in the disinfection rate due to an internal photo-Fenton mechanism within the cell. With this particular exception, it can be concluded that most of the naturally occurring substances in water mainly affect the performance of the SODIS process in high-volume containers by their potential role as attenuators of light. The potential role of the external substances in electron transfer mechanisms is completely overshadowed by the loss of radiation in the total volume of the container.

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1. Introduction

On 28th July 2010, the United Nations General Assembly recognized the human right to water and sanitation, declaring that clean drinking water and sanitation are essential to fulfil all human rights. In September 2015, the same assembly announced the Sustainable Development Goals in order to “end poverty in all its forms” by the action plan called the 2030 Agenda. Goal 6 aims to “Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all”, including eight global targets related to the management of the natural water resource, wastewater and environment. The first target is to “Achieve access to safe and affordable drinking water” and ensure access to drinking water. Currently, 844 million people still lack access to safe drinking water and approximately 1000 children daily die due to diseases related to safe drinking water and sanitation [1,2].

Most of the population without access to safe water resources is located in rural areas of low-income countries. Communities obtain water mainly from dug wells, rainwater and springs without any built-in water treatment, representing a high microbiological risk. For example, a ten-year (2004–2014) report in West Amhara (Ethiopia) shows that water samples from 52.0% of wells and 20.2% of springs were positive for the faecal contamination indicator *E. coli* [3]. This situation is caused by inadequate management or lack of resources and/or knowledge of water treatment. The World Health Organization (WHO) has established the Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality (GDWQ) [4] and recommended procedures for storage, use and consumption of drinking water. According to this guide, the safety of drinking water should be assured with regular testing for faecal contamination. In addition to the monitoring of faecal bacteria concentration, it is recommended to measure physicochemical properties of water such as pH, turbidity, organic matter or metals dissolved in water since they can impact upon the effectiveness of disinfection.

Disinfection is of absolute importance in the supply of safe drinking water. The destruction of pathogenic microorganisms is essential, but in low-income countries, the extreme limitations of facilities and financial resources impede the application of conventional water treatment processes. In these cases, household water treatments (HWT) are suitable low cost, easy to use and sustainable options. They have the potential to disinfect water in situations where people rely on source water that may be contaminated or where stored water becomes contaminated because of unhygienic handling during collection and transport to the home. Examples of common HWT include boiling, chlorination, filtration, flocculation and solar disinfection (SODIS). The latter is based on the harmful effect of the UV radiation and temperature on pathogens in unsafe water. Usually, water is exposed in 2 L PET bottles for 6 h in sunny days or 48 h in cloudy conditions [5]. Alternative container materials can be used, such as glass or other plastics which transmit more solar UV than PET. However, glass is fragile and is a potential source of injury [6] while other plastics can increase the production costs or have poor photostability [7]. A transparent water container is the only requirement for SODIS, making it the cheapest form of HWT, with an estimated cost of \$0.63 per person per year, versus \$0.66 for chlorination, \$3.03 for filtration and \$4.95 for flocculation [8].

However, SODIS presents some drawbacks that limits its widespread adoption. One is the limited volume of the bottles, with a maximum of 2 L per batch, and therefore they are needed many small containers in parallel to provide sufficient quantity for a standard household. In Sub-Saharan Africa, plastic jerrycans of 25 L are containers universally employed for water collection and transport. Standard jerrycans are typically made of opaque HDPE plastic. Consequently, the use of transparent jerrycans that allow the application of SODIS process is a challenge that could be an alternative and easy to implement HWT in this region [9]. However, increasing the volume of the SODIS containers must be carefully addressed to ensure that the effect of water characteristics on the radiation distribution (transmission and

scattering) is considered in order to make an in-depth appraisal of the required exposure time. Another challenge is the variability of the weather conditions and water characteristics that necessitate the incorporation of a significant safety factor into the standard recommended exposure time from 6 h on sunny days to up to 48 h in cloudy conditions. The reason is that the irradiance, temperature and water composition modify significantly the inactivation efficacy [10].

The mechanism of solar disinfection can involve three types of photoinduced damage on pathogens [10]: i) Direct endogenous damage, ii) Indirect endogenous damage, iii) Indirect exogenous damage. Endogenous damage (i and ii) involve intracellular processes. Direct damage (i) is caused by absorption of radiation by components within the pathogen, indirect damage (ii) is the result of an interaction between a component of the pathogen and an internal photo-produced reactive intermediate (PPRI) which has been activated by solar photons. Both types of damage are difficult to separate and so are usually studied in combination. Substances present in the water can also absorb radiation and/or produce external PPRI. If the external PPRI leads to damage to the pathogen, the process is called indirect exogenous damage (iii) and improves inactivation [10]. In contrast, if they only absorb radiation, they produce a decrease in the radiation received by the pathogen and, consequently, the efficacy of the inactivation is reduced. In this case, the substances can be considered as attenuation factor. In 2011, Kirk [11] defined a diffuse downwelling attenuation coefficient to calculate the transmission of irradiance over a depth interval in a water column. However, it is an empirical parameter that have to be measured for every particular water. For this reason, it is important to analyse the effect of each component of water and obtain mechanistic models that predict the attenuation of irradiance and the required solar exposure time as a function of water composition.

This work presents an experimental evaluation of the SODIS process in high-volume (25 L rather than the typical 2 L) PET containers as a function of the concentration of the naturally occurring substances in the water. An in-depth study of the radiation attenuation caused by these substances is conducted to validate a predictive model that estimates the required solar exposure time based on the average radiation intensity and its uniformity within the container.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Water composition

Model substances commonly found in water sources in Sub-Saharan regions were employed to assess the effect of the water composition on the SODIS process. These substances include bicarbonate, iron ions, soluble carbohydrates, humic acids and suspended solids. Iron was added as FeSO_4 , which is oxidized to Fe(III) at pH 7.3 by dissolved oxygen in water, involving a variety of partially oxidized meta-stable intermediates that transform into stable iron oxide end-products such as hematite, magnetite, goethite and lepidocrocite [12–14]. Presence of solids and the associated subsequent turbidity was modelled using red soil whose characteristics and procedure for preparation has been described in previous studies [15,16]. Sucrose was added as soluble carbohydrate to achieve the desired level of dissolved organic carbon (DOC). All parameters were independently checked at different concentration levels with maximum initial values of 20 mg/L DOC of soluble carbohydrates, 100 ppm bicarbonate, 3 ppm of Fe, 20 ppm of humic acids and 100 NTU of turbidity. All of them exceed the values commonly reported in Sub-Saharan water sources to ensure the evaluation of real conditions [17,18]. Transmission spectra, and absorption and scattering coefficients of significant substances were experimentally determined with a Varian Cary 500 spectrophotometer.

2.2. Disinfection experiments

Experiments were carried out with tap water upon addition of

sodium thiosulfate to remove residual chlorine before bacterial inoculation. Wild *E. coli* sp. in the role of a model microorganism was isolated from wastewater from the Rey Juan Carlos university (Móstoles, Spain) sewage plant and was inoculated with an initial concentration of 10^3 CFU/mL, ensuring applicability to the reported typical field concentrations of 1 CFU/mL [17,18] or 100 CFU/mL [19]. Fresh liquid cultures were prepared by inoculation in Luria-Bertani (LB) nutrient medium and incubation at 37 °C with rotary shaking for 24 h. To prepare the reaction media, 5 mL of the liquid culture were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min. Bacteria were separated from supernatant, rinsed again with 5 mL of sterile saline solution (NaCl 0.9%), and diluted into the experimental container to obtain the initial concentration. Samples taken during the experiments were analysed using the standard serial dilution method and plating in LB agar with the colonies counted after incubation for 24 h at 37 °C. The detection limit of this method was 1 CFU/mL. The experimental temperature was set on 25 °C.

2.3. Experimental system

Sunlight illumination was simulated under controlled conditions with a xenon lamp (Osram XBO 5000 W/H XL) with a temperature colour of 6000 K located on a customized reflector to ensure adequate homogeneous illumination of the water container. The emission spectrum of this lamp matches satisfactorily with the solar spectrum at the Earth surface in the UV range [20]. Irradiance at the surface of the container was measured by spectroradiometry using a calibrated StellarNet Spectrometer UVIS-25 (329–400 nm). The experiments were carried out at UV irradiance values of 0, 11.3, 16.6, 21.6 and 28.2 W/m².

The experiments were performed in 25 L PET containers 525.9 mm tall and with a base of 240.5 by 262.6 mm with an average wall thickness of 0.55 mm.

2.4. Modelling of the radiation distribution

Numerical simulations for modelling the radiation transport as a function of water composition in the SODIS containers were developed using ANSYS® Fluent v.14.5 (ANSYS Inc.). First, the water container was geometrically defined using the ANSYS® Workbench tool (Fig. S.1) which includes three parts: i) an air hexahedral domain, ii) the container domain that is beneath the air region and has the absorption coefficient of PET (42.14 m^{-1}) and iii) the water domain that fills the interior of the container. A boundary condition was set in one lateral face of the hexahedron to transmit the radiation received from the light source. All the domains were meshed with total volumetric cells of 228,897 using ANSYS® meshing tool (Fig. S.1). The number of cells was determined to be sufficiently high to provide mesh independent simulation results of the global incident radiation and net radiation fluxes with a relative error below of 10^{-6} .

The calculation of the radiation field requires the solution of the Radiative Transfer Equation (RTE) (Eq. (1)) [21]:

$$\frac{dI(\vec{r}, \vec{s})}{ds} + (\kappa + \sigma_s) \cdot I(\vec{r}, \vec{s}) = \kappa \cdot n^2 \cdot \frac{\sigma \cdot T^4}{\pi} + \frac{\sigma_s}{4\pi} \cdot \int_0^{4\pi} I(\vec{r}, \vec{s}') \cdot \Phi(\vec{s} \cdot \vec{s}') \cdot d\Omega' \quad (1)$$

where \vec{r} and \vec{s} are the position and direction vectors, s the path length, I the radiation intensity, κ and σ_s are the absorption and scattering coefficients, respectively, n the refraction index, σ the Stefan-Boltzmann constant ($5.669 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}^4$), T the local temperature and Φ is the phase function that describes the scattering event.

Numerical solution of the RTE was carried out using the Discrete Ordinates Method (DOM). This method solves the radiative values at any point of the geometry for a finite number of discrete solid angles, each one associated with a direction vector. When the DOM is used, the spatial discretization is taken from the mesh, but an angular

discretization is also required. The emission in 3D shapes a sphere formed with eight octants. 15×15 divisions and 1×1 pixels defined each octant to avoid the “ray effect” and angle overhanging respectively.

All the inter-domains surfaces were set as semi-transparent and zero-thickness. As the emission of radiation can be neglected at the low operation temperatures of the process, the temperature was fixed to 1 K in all domains to inactivate calculations of radiation emission. The water (bacterial suspension and water components) was considered as a homogenous medium with a refractive index of 1.33 (refractive index of water). Presence of bacteria does not affect the radiative transmission. Catalase (CAT) and superoxide dismutase (SOD) enzymes and nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NADH) were considered as the absorption components of the bacteria. The specific absorption coefficients (κ^*) were obtained from the literature, using an average value in the UV-A range (300–400 nm): κ_{CAT}^* as $2.6 \cdot 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$ [22]; κ_{SOD}^* as $800 \text{ M}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$ [23]; and κ_{NADH}^* as $6220 \text{ M}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$ [24]. Values of the absorption volumetric coefficients were estimated by assuming:

- i) A bacterial volume of $1.96 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^3$ for a typical size of *E. coli* of $1 \mu\text{m}$ in length and $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter.
- ii) Initial bacterial concentration of 10^3 CFU/mL.
- iii) A constant NADH concentration at the basal *E. coli* concentration of $2.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ [25].
- iv) Initial concentrations of CAT and SOD in the cell of $9.2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ [26,27] and $2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ [28].

The resulting values were $3.05 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $4.68 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3.19 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for NADH, CAT and SOD, respectively. These values are sufficiently low that we can safely disregard any effect of the bacteria on the radiation field. However, absorption and scattering coefficients of water components (calculated in this work) were included in the model resolution as extinction coefficients of the water. The Henyey-Greenstein phase function [29] was included in the model as a User Defined Function (UDF), using an averaged value of g_λ for the whole UV-A range. All these values can be considered constant with the time as well as the radiation intensities, being solved the radiation field in steady state. The main output parameters calculated from the simulations were the average incident radiation, its uniformity index, and the average radiation flux at the rear internal face of the container.

A second-order upwind discretization scheme was used to solve the DOM equations. The simulations were carried out using the double-precision solver and with standard values of the under-relaxation factors due to good convergence and reasonable computational time. Scaled residuals of the numerical solution were monitored, considering that the equations converged when residuals (relative errors) achieved a value of 10^{-6} for incident radiation and energy.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of dissolved substances on the SODIS process in high-volume containers

Bacterial inactivation experiments were carried out to check the effect of the water composition on the SODIS process efficacy. Iron, solids, bicarbonates, soluble carbohydrates and humic acids were individually added to the water to assess the effect of common substances found in Sub-Saharan waters. Results were analysed based on the reduction of the viable bacteria count in comparison with unaltered water as a reference.

The presence of substances in the water can limit the radiation received by pathogens (increasing the required inactivation time) or can improve the inactivation if they produce external PPRI or encourage the internal harmful process. According to the results shown in Fig. 1.A, none of the substances enhanced the inactivation at the studied concentrations. A negligible effect is observed for the presence in water of

Fig. 1. Effect of the presence of carbohydrates, bicarbonates, humic acids, iron, and solids: A) on the bacterial inactivation efficiency of the SODIS process for a UV irradiance of 28.2 W/m², B) on water transmission spectra.

bicarbonates and soluble carbohydrates. In contrast, the presence of iron, and especially of humic acids and solids show a dramatic impact on the efficacy of the process. This effect can be attributed to the interference of the different substances in the transport of radiation which is confirmed by the transmission spectra in Fig. 1.B. Whereas the transmission spectrum of the reference water is not significantly modified by the presence of soluble carbohydrates or bicarbonates, iron and especially humic acids and solids dramatically reduce the available radiation for the solar disinfection process. Therefore, it can be concluded that a clear qualitative correlation between the transmission spectra and the inactivation curves is observed.

In order to analyse the correlation between the radiation transfer and the disinfection efficacy from a quantitative approach, the optical properties of the UV active substances were obtained. The absorption (κ) and scattering (σ) coefficients and the scattering phase function of the water with the different substances were experimentally determined from transmittance (direct and diffuse) and reflectance spectra at increasing concentrations, following the procedure reported elsewhere [30]. Thus, Table 1 shows κ and σ coefficients and g parameter of the Henyey-Greenstein scattering phase function. Results of Table 1 confirm that, in the case of solids, the attenuation is mainly due to radiation scattering, whereas for iron and humic acids the extinction is caused by photon absorption. As the radiation received by the bacteria is lower, more exposure time is required to achieve the same

Table 1
Absorption (κ) and scattering (σ) coefficients and g parameter of the Henyey-Greenstein scattering phase function for solids, dissolved iron and humic acids.

	Solids (cm ⁻¹ .NTU ⁻¹)	Iron (cm ⁻¹ .ppm ⁻¹)	Humic Acids (cm ⁻¹ .ppm ⁻¹)
κ	$(2.40 \pm 2.00) \times 10^{-4}$	$(7.82 \pm 0.33) \times 10^{-2}$	$(1.20 \pm 0.28) \times 10^{-2}$
σ	$(7.39 \pm 0.21) \times 10^{-3}$	–	–
g	0.5246 (dimensionless)	–	–

inactivation efficacy for the same level of irradiance. Consequently, these results confirm the hypothesis that the presence of solids, humic acids, and iron in water impacts negatively on the disinfection process through their role as radiation attenuation factors. In contrast, the presence of non-optically active organic or inorganic substances in the water, such as carbohydrates or bicarbonates, does not significantly affect the process.

3.2. Effect of the concentration of optically active substances.

The effects of solids, humic acids, and iron were studied at different concentrations (Fig. 2) and UV irradiance levels (Fig. S.2). In the case of the substances that only absorb radiation (iron and humic acids), their concentration values were selected to achieve in both cases exactly the same volumetric absorption in the container calculated as the product of the specific absorption coefficient by the concentration of each substance. The absorption of radiation reduces significantly the photons available for the bacteria, negatively impacting on the inactivation profiles. However, when comparing the results in Fig. 2.A and 2.B, it is clearly observed that humic acids have a more negative impact than iron whose effect is also unfavourable. Consequently, these results suggest that both substances present different behaviours that cannot be exclusively explained by their optical properties and that would require the quantitative analysis of the radiation transfer in the container, as discussed later.

In the case of turbidity, the scattering of photons leads to some radiation losses through the sides of the container, reducing the total amount of radiation available to be absorbed by the bacteria in the water, leading to a lower bacterial inactivation. As can be observed in Fig. 2.C, the results obtained for very turbid water are close to the reference experiments in the dark. However, a quantitative evaluation of the radiation transfer in the container would be also required to conclude whether the effect of the solids is exclusively due to the optical effect of the particles or additional phenomena should be considered.

3.3. Quantitative evaluation of radiation transfer in the container

Figs. 3 and 4 show the distribution of radiation inside the volume of the container for different concentrations of the optically active substances. Although in both cases a non-homogeneous distribution of radiation is observed, significant differences appear depending on the absorption or scattering nature of the attenuation. Absorption by iron and humic acids (Fig. 3) led to a progressive decrease of incident radiation along with the container as the radiation pathway length increases. In contrast, the scattering generated by the particles (Fig. 4) led to significantly more pronounced profiles with much higher values of incident radiation close to the front side, even above the irradiance.

Experimental radiometric measurements at the rear of the container were successfully used for the validation of the radiation modelling predictions (Figs. 5 and 6). A total of 36 measurements homogeneously distributed in a grid of 4 columns \times 9 rows were recorded to calculate the experimental average radiation flux and its standard deviation, higher as the radiation inhomogeneity increases and also subjected to the experimental error. These values were compared with the theoretical values calculated by the simulations (Figs. 5 and 6), showing a

Fig. 2. Effect of the concentration of the optically active substances in water on the SODIS process for an UV irradiance of 28.2 W/m². A) Humic acids, B) Iron, C) Solids.

very good agreement (Tables 2 and 3) that validates how the container is irradiated and the optical properties of the aqueous substances. In both cases, the radiation flux at the rear face decreased dramatically with the increase in the optical density of the water, increasing the optical extinction (either due to absorption or scattering) and leading to complete darkness when the concentration of the optically active substances is high enough.

3.4. Effect on the *E. coli* inactivation kinetics

Considering the photoactivated nature of the bacterial inactivation process, the disinfection rate should be proportional to the average incident radiation in the water volume according to Eq. (2):

$$k = k_0 \cdot G \tag{2}$$

where k is the pseudo first-order kinetic constant experimentally calculated for a specific incident radiation value (min⁻¹), k_0 is the radiation independent kinetic factor (m²/W·min) and G is the average incident radiation in the container volume (W/m²).

Experiments in reference water without the presence of optically active substances were carried out at different irradiance levels of 11.3, 16.6, 21.6 and 28.2 W/m² (Fig. 7). k_0 can be estimated from the experimental values of the kinetic constant, k , and the values of the average incident radiation, G , calculated by the radiation transport simulation. These values are shown in Table 4 and were fitted to Eq. (2) to determine a value of 2.81·10⁻³ m²/W·min for k_0 (R² = 0.999) and a Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE) of 3.09%.

When optically active substances are present in the water, the attenuation of radiation leads to a significant decrease in the average incident radiation as shown in Tables 5 and 6. Considering that the bacterial inactivation rate is strongly dependent on the availability of photons, this reduction in the incident radiation should impact on the efficiency of the disinfection process. Estimates of the kinetic constant values for the inactivation experiments in the presence of optically active substances can be calculated using Eq. (2) with the value of k_0 calculated from the reference experiments and the values of G calculated from the radiation transport simulations (Tables 5 and 6). Fig. 8.A shows the comparison between the experimental and the predicted kinetic constants for water with iron, humic acids, and solids. As can be seen, the agreement of the results is poor, with high correlation error values in all cases (NRMSE values of 66%, 31% and 59% for solids, humic acids, and iron, respectively).

A possible explanation for the unsuccessful predictions of Eq. (2) model is that the process is not only affected by the average value of the incident radiation, but also by the homogeneity in the distribution of the radiation in the container. In low-volume containers, differences in radiation distribution could be neglected due to the short optical path. However, in high volume containers, the radiation distribution is very inhomogeneous (Figs. 3 and 4), suggesting the necessity of correction for the value of G in the estimation of the kinetic constant according to Eq. (3):

$$k = k_0 \cdot G \cdot UI \tag{3}$$

where UI is the uniformity index of the radiation distribution in the container, whose value can be estimated from the results of the radiation transport simulations (Tables 5 and 6). The use of the UI allows us to integrate in the model the significant differences existing in the radiation distribution for similar values of G when the extinction is mainly produced by absorption or by scattering effects (Fig. S.3). As an example, for the same irradiance and the same calculated value of the average incident radiation in the total volume of the container of 12 W/m², the UI value for iron and humic acids (predominantly absorption) is

Fig. 3. Distribution of the incident radiation (W/m^2) in the longitudinal axis for different levels of iron and humic acids concentration for a UV-A irradiance in the front side (left in the plot) of $28.2 W/m^2$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

0.8, much higher than the 0.5 value for the solids (predominantly scattering).

Although pure water neither absorbs nor scatters radiation, the large size of the container and the refractive index of water (1.33) lead to small radiation losses through container walls and, consequently, the decrease of incident radiation along the container and a uniformity index slightly lower than one (0.94). The radiation distribution along the container with pure water can be seen in Figs. 3 and 5 (0 ppm) or Figs. 4 and 6 (0 NTU). A value of $k_0 = 2.99 \cdot 10^{-3} m^2/W \cdot min$ ($R^2 = 0.999$, NRMSE = 3.09%) was recalculated using the reference experiments with pure water.

Fig. 8.B show the comparison of the experimental kinetic constants with the new kinetic constant values calculated with Eq. (3). In this case, a good agreement is observed for the presence of solids and humic acids, with reasonable values of NRMSE of 22% and 20%, respectively. In contrast, Fig. 8.B shows that the values of the kinetic constants of experiments in the presence of iron are always higher than those estimated by the model. The same optical properties and radiation distribution led to significantly different results when the absorption is produced by humic acids or by iron, with a NRMSE of 69% for the latter.

In 2019, Kohantorabi et al. [31] found that the presence of natural organic matter (NOM) or humic acids (HA) at concentrations lower than 7 ppm can enhance the disinfection rate when the process is carried out in low-volume reactors (Pyrex glass bottle). Absorption of UV light by NOM produces the corresponding triplet states ($^3NOM^*$), and the

formation of singlet oxygen and derived reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can damage bacteria [31,32]. They also found that a concentration as low as 1 mg/L of ferrous iron also enhanced the disinfection rate since iron permeates into the cell and reacts with dissolved oxygen to generate ROS that damage the bacteria [31,32]. These results observed in optically clear water and short optical path devices cannot be extrapolated to high-volume containers where the higher optical path-length of the medium introduces radiation transport limitations. In this case, the presence of optically active species significantly reduces the availability of photons, counteracting the potential enhancement of the process by their role in electron transfer processes. Therefore, the bacterial damage produced by external ROS is completely overshadowed by the loss of radiation in the total volume of the container, as the fitting of the results to the radiation attenuation model proves for HA. In contrast, in the case of iron, its permeation inside the cell leads to a more effective damaging process partially counteracting the radiation attenuation role. Therefore, in this case, the experimental inactivation results are significantly better than those predicted by the pure radiation attenuation model. Evidence of the latter hypothesis was provided in 2018 by Giannakis et al. [33] by comparing the inactivation kinetics of a standard *E. coli* strain (in which iron outside the cell can permeate through the membrane porins) with a porinless mutant *E. coli* strain in which iron permeation is hindered. They observed that iron permeates into the *E. coli* cell and enhances the damage produced by an intracellular Fenton process. Those experiments, carried out in 100 mL of pure water in which a UI close to 1.0 could be

Fig. 4. Distribution of the incident radiation (W/m^2) in the longitudinal axis for different levels of turbidity for a UV-A irradiance in the front side (left in the plot) of $28.2 W/m^2$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Radiation flux (W/m^2) in the backside for different levels of iron concentration used for validation of iron optical properties for a UV-A irradiance in the front side of $28.2 W/m^2$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. Radiation flux (W/m^2) in the backside for different levels of turbidity used for validation of red soil optical properties for a UV-A irradiance in the front side of $28.2 W/m^2$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2

Experimental and simulated average radiation flux (W/m^2) on the rear side of the container for different levels of iron and humic acids concentration for UV-A irradiance in the front side of $28.2 W/m^2$.

Iron/ Humic acids	0 ppm/ 0 ppm	0.5 ppm/ 3.26 ppm	1 ppm/ 6.53 ppm	2 ppm/ 13.1 ppm	3 ppm/ 19.6 ppm
Experimental	18.1 ± 11.4	5.3 ± 2.8	3.4 ± 1.7	1.4 ± 0.6	1.3 ± 0.7
Simulated	17.2 ± 3.4	7.0 ± 0.9	3.1 ± 0.6	0.9 ± 0.6	0.6 ± 0.5

Table 3

Experimental and simulated average radiation flux (W/m^2) at the rear face of the container for different levels of turbidity for UV-A irradiance in the front side of $28.2 W/m^2$.

Solids	0 NTU	20 NTU	50 NTU	100 NTU
Experimental	18.1 ± 11.4	4.5 ± 1.8	1.4 ± 0.4	0.8 ± 0.2
Simulated	17.2 ± 3.4	3.5 ± 0.4	1.1 ± 0.3	0.5 ± 0.4

assumed, show an improvement in the disinfection rate. In contrast, in high volume containers, the decrease in the values of G and UI counteracts this effect, as the experiment with 1 ppm of iron confirms (Fig. 2.B), with a kinetic constant very similar to that of the reference water. Consequently, whereas solids and humic acids impact negatively

on the efficacy of the solar disinfection process by their role as radiation attenuator, the effect of the presence of iron depends on a compromise between its detrimental role in the attenuation of radiation and its beneficial enhancement of the internal damage due to its permeation into the bacterial cell.

4. Conclusions

This comprehensive study confirms the feasibility of applying the SODIS process in high-volume containers for water disinfection under a wide range of experimental conditions. However, it is clearly demonstrated that the required exposure time to achieve total bacterial inactivation is strongly dependent on water composition. While the presence of substances transparent in the UVA range such as bicarbonates and soluble carbohydrates do not lead to any impact in the disinfection

Fig. 7. Effect of irradiance on the *E. coli* inactivation in reference water without optically active substances.

Table 4

Average incident radiation and kinetic constants of the experiments of *E. coli* inactivation in reference water without optically active substances for increasing irradiance values.

Irradiance (W/m ²)	Average Incident Radiation, G (W/m ²)	k (min ⁻¹)
11.3	8.90	2.61·10 ⁻²
16.6	13.0	3.44·10 ⁻²
21.6	17.0	4.83·10 ⁻²
28.2	22.2	6.28·10 ⁻²

Table 5

Average incident radiation and uniformity index in the volume of the high-volume container as a function of iron or humic acids concentration.

	0 ppm/	0.5 ppm/	1 ppm/	2 ppm/	3 ppm/
Iron/ Humic acids	0 ppm	3.26 ppm	6.53 ppm	13.1 ppm	19.6 ppm
G (W/m ²)	22.2	14.4	10.1	5.97	4.10
UI	0.94	0.86	0.76	0.59	0.49

Table 6

Average incident radiation and uniformity index in the total volume of the high-volume container as a function of solids concentration.

Solids	0 NTU	20 NTU	50 NTU	100 NTU
G (W/m ²)	22.2	20.7	17.3	12.8
UI	0.94	0.80	0.65	0.53

rate, optically active substance such as iron, humic acids, or solids strongly affect it. These three substances were found to be attenuating factors in high-volume containers where the potential role of the external substances in electron transport mechanism is completely overshadowed by the loss of radiation in the total volume of the container. In the case of iron, its permeation inside the cells contributes to the intracellular Fenton process enhancing the bacterial damage.

The quantitative determination of the optical properties of the optically active substances and the simulation of the radiation transport is proven to be critical for the determination of the average incident radiation and the uniformity index inside high-volume containers where a strongly inhomogeneous distribution of radiation influences the disinfection rate.

Finally, the simple kinetic modelling approach developed in this work is shown as a valuable tool to predict the efficacy of the process

Fig. 8. Comparison of experimental first-order kinetic constant for *E. coli* photoinactivation and estimated of the kinetic model of radiation attenuating substances. A) kinetic model for low-volume containers, B) Kinetic model for high-volume containers.

for a given irradiance and water composition, leading to satisfactory forecasting of the required exposure time for water in presence of bicarbonates, soluble carbohydrates, humic acids, and solids in high-volume containers. Further work should be done to integrate in the predictions the quantitative effect of particular substances such as iron whose role is not exclusively optical.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.125852>.

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